

Methodology to assess the role of legume crops and mixes in supporting pollinators

Problem

75% of the world's crops rely on pollinators for seed set. Across the globe, insect pollinator populations are in decline: low pollinator abundance can cause up to 80% yield gaps for some crops, compromising food production. Flowering legumes provide nectar, pollen and habitat for many insect species, but legumes form a small proportion of crops grown in UK arable farmland.

Solution

A methodology was applied to assess legume crops and legume-based mixtures, trialled at multiple farm sites, for their contribution to floral resource provision and pollinator abundance.

Benefits

Addition of legumes as main crops or legume mixtures for soil improvement (green manures) led to increased numbers of floral units per unit area of ground. Insect pollinator abundance was highest in the presence of legumes compared with non-legume (cereal) crops.

Applicability box

Theme

Ecosystem services from legume crops

Keywords

Legume mixtures, legume crops, faba bean

Context

Scotland, rest of the UK

Application time

Spring (sowing) to summer (harvest)

Required time

An annual crop growing season

Period of impact

An annual growing season

Equipment

Drills and combines capable of handling legume seeds; insect pollinator guide

Best in

Arable cropping

Practical recommendations

- Flowering legumes can be grown as legume mixes (e.g. as green manures or cover crops) or as legume crops (e.g. faba beans) or intercrops.
- When legumes are in flower (typically May-July in the UK), the number of flowers per unit area of ground indicates the level of floral resources (pollen, nectar) available to insect pollinators.
- Pollinator abundance and activity can be determined by carrying out transect counts. This involves walking at a steady speed along a defined distance in the crop and counting the number and type of pollinators foraging or resting on flowers within a 1 m strip either side of the observer.
- Legumes provide a greater density of floral units (flowerheads) than non-legume crops like cereals (e.g. oat, barley), with greatest numbers depending on the timing of flowering of each species (**Figure 1A**). Floral resources in cereal crops are provided by flowering weed species.

Crimson clover-based legume mix (A) and faba bean crop (B) trialled in farmers' fields (Jacqui Brandt, Nicola Dempster).

- Pollinators are observed at higher abundance in legumes compared with non-legumes like cereals (Figure 1B). Pollinators visits in cereal crops are confined to arable weed flowers. The most common visitors are bumblebee species, hoverfly species, and butterfly species.

Figure 1. (A) The floral resources (average number of flowers per 0.25 m²) in plots containing a legume mix or oat crop. The legume mix provided a greater density of floral units than oat, with most of the flowerheads associated with clover, seradella and weeds. Floral resources were greater in June than in July. (B) The average number of insect pollinators observed during a 50 m transect walk in plots of the legume mix or oat crop. Pollinators were observed at higher abundance in the legume mix. A total of 18 species were observed, approx. 40% were bumblebee species, 40% hoverfly species, and 20% were butterfly species. The data was collected from a farm trial in the Scottish Borders carried out in 2025.

Further information

For more practical recommendations, see:

- Pollinator transect guide: https://csc.hutton.ac.uk/resource/Handbook_of_indicators_v1.pdf
- Bumblebee identification guide: <https://www.bumblebeeconservation.org/learn-about-bumblebees/species-guide/>
- Butterfly identification guide: <https://butterfly-conservation.org/butterflies/identify-a-butterfly>
- Hoverfly identification guide: <https://bna-naturalists.org/id-guide-hoverflies/>
- Guide for improving farmland biodiversity using flowering mixes: <https://ahdb.org.uk/knowledge-library/using-flowering-seed-mixes-to-improve-farmland-biodiversity>

About this practice abstract

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Project website: www.legumesproject.eu

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